

Family education: Instilling career expectations for woman

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ABSTRACT

Because women in Indonesian society gain more experience in the family, one of which is education instilled through family gender culture, women's career aspirations are believed to have their own characteristics. In today's society, the current condition of female students' career expectations is apprehensive. Most of the female students do not have any professional characteristics, such as career aspirations. This research involving 109 female students from various cultural contexts will divide their findings into two categories: patriarchal family education and matriarchal family education. The main objective of this research is to investigate the career expectations of female students in relation to patriarchal and matriarchal family education, and to compare the two household categories. As a result, the majority of female students from societies that place a patriarchal emphasis on gender have expectations of career self-efficacy, whereas those from societies that place a matriarchal emphasis on gender have expectations of outcomes. Parametric analysis of variance (ANOVA) test was used for comparative analysis. The test results show $F = 75.011$ for career expectations on self-efficacy and $F = 145.467$ for outcome expectation (OE). 0.000 is a significant value for both variations.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Significant in human development, adolescence is characterized by a number of variables that necessitate the attainment of maturity; consequently, a large number of specialists endeavor to comprehend this stage. According to cognitive psychology, individuals between the ages of 12 and 22 are considered to be in the formal operational period of development. The human race has reached this stage when it has attained cognitive maturity, which is characterized by the ability to manipulate the concepts that they think about as well as the capacity to implement these ideas in the actual world [1]–[3]. In social psychology, this situation is referred to as the identity exploration phase. It is characterized by the capacity to perform social responsibilities in tandem with bodily changes (puberty) that give rise to experiences responsible for the formation of identity [4], [5].

Brown and Lent [6] explained that human mental development during adolescence experiences a Peak Condition, which can be seen from behavior or in career and job conditions can be seen from the career choices that they decide. In addition to being related to the aforementioned, the adolescent phase is an

important phase in the career development of humans. Brown and Lent [6] explained the psychosocial conditions of adolescents that are related to aspects of career and job development. Their explanation was based on the behavioristic theory developed by Albert Bandura, and they explained that there were seven related variables starting from personal attributes, learning experiences, career expectations, career interests, career choice, choice action, and career performance, as well as social support as a moderate variable that influences career choice. Ireland and Lent [7] also explained that there were seven related variables starting from personal. These seven variables, along with one more component that serves as an intermediary, come together to form a new theory that is subsequently referred to as the social cognitive career theory (SCCT) [6], [7]. To see how each component is related, see Figure 1.

Figure 1. Framework of SCCT [6]

Problems associated with this condition become intriguing when adolescents are involved, because adolescents possess personal characteristics such as predisposition, gender, race/ethnicity, physical health status, and other influences. The unique personal characteristics of each adolescent have varying effects on the experience that becomes a lesson for him in his daily life. This situation will directly provide and instill in him career expectations regarding self-efficacy expectation (SEE) and outcome expectation (OE). Self-efficacy refers to how individuals assess their abilities in an unperformed activity, whereas OE refers to the ability to offer opinions on the results, carried out in specific activities. SEE describes X's belief that he is capable of becoming an athlete like his father, based on the personal characteristics he possesses as the son of a soccer player. Then, Y desires to become an expert in architecture because he believes he will obtain a decent job with a high salary; this is known as an OE [6], [8], [9].

Expectations regarding one's career led to decisions regarding one's career that are made by people; decisions regarding one's career that are made will affect actions and performance regarding one's career, which are then translated into daily behavior. The social support that is provided by the surroundings, whether in the form of approbation or prohibition, has an effect on this scenario. This circumstance is referred to as a variable, and it plays a significant role in determining the conditions of career development and work, particularly for teens. The findings of other studies in addition to those carried out by Brown and Lent [6], Mackowiak and Eckel [10] offer a more comprehensive explanation of the factors that influence the progression of a career or a job. Savickas performed study to determine the extent to which learning expectations and career expectations influence profession choices. During the course of his research, Savickas discovered an additional variable that exists between learning expectation and career expectation; he referred to this variable as life design [6], [10].

In a distinct research study conducted by Betz, the author paid special attention to adolescents' developing SEE. This scenario is related to one's career performance, which is reflected in their daily actions. As evidenced by his inclusion of self-beliefs as a variable that determines one's sense of self-efficacy, Life *et al.* [11] also gives attention to this aspect. The results of this study indicate that adolescent self-confidence has a positive effect on their self-efficacy in making decisions regarding their future careers. Based on investigations conducted by Ireland and Lent [7], Brown and Lent [6] and Life *et al.* [11], the findings contribute to a deeper understanding of SCCT [6], [11]–[15].

Teenagers in the Indonesian culture frequently find themselves unable to choose a career path. The personal characteristics he possesses and the learning experiences he gains from interacting with the environment are frequently contradictory. JU is a student majoring in political science, experienced perplexity when confronted with a situation to determine her desired career path. The fact that JU is the son of a regional service leader with influence over the political situation in the region inspires confidence in JU's

ability to pursue a successful political career in the future. This circumstance contrasts with the knowledge he acquired from a social environment that honors physicians. Therefore, this circumstance makes it difficult for JU to decide where to pursue a career [14].

One of the predispositions posited by the SCCT theory is the existence of gender cultural factors that influence the personal characteristics of adolescents; in this regard, the development of women differs from that of men. Brown and Lent [6] provides an intriguing description of this predisposition, the contribution of gender culture to the family, which is created as a result of the fact that cultural education from childhood creates unique variations in each person. Men who have had positive cultural experiences since childhood with patriarchs will have patriarchal views and therefore choose patriarchal jobs, while women who have had positive cultural experiences with matriarchs will have matriarchal views and choose matriarchal jobs. the patrilineal. This condition illustrates how gender conditions will affect the career development of humans differently throughout their lifetimes. In addition, in eastern culture, women tend to gain more learning experience from their families than from their play environments; it is on the basis of this supposition that women were selected as the subject of this study [6], [16], [17].

In this article, the ideas that were talked about before are limited to learning experiences that are directly tied to gender culture in the family and to the career expectations of students who are still building their careers. Students have hit the stage of career consolidation because they are now working with a professional to get ready for work. The goal of this study is to give an overview of the different parts of students' job goals based on the gender culture they learn at home.

2. METHOD

This study compares two or more factors to use a quantitative design with a comparative method. This study looked at the effects of patriarchal (X1) and matriarchal (X2) cultural, demographic, and gender factors on career expectations of self-efficacy (Y1) and career expectations of outcome (Y2). Participants in this study were female undergraduate students studying in the Islamic Education Guidance and Counseling Department, Faculty of Tarbiyah and Teaching Science, Institut Agama Islam Negeri Kerinci. The population was 149 people, then the sample size was determined using the Slovin sample determination formula with a confidence level of 95%, from this calculation the sample size was determined; namely as many as 109 people. then grouped into two cultural backgrounds, namely matriarchal and patriarchal. With proportional sampling, 55 samples were obtained from a matriarchal cultural background and 54 samples from a patriarchal cultural background. Then participants belonging to this sample were selected using a purposive random sampling method. by setting the sample in a relatively similar age range (19-21 years), a cultural background that is not influenced by other cultures (father, mother and family have the same cultural background and no personnel married outside the family's gender culture) [18], [19].

The research tool is based on Walby's [20] idea of gender culture, which divides gender culture into patriarchal and matriarchal groups. in Indonesia, specifically in central Sumatra. Gender cultures form their own groups with their own land ownership, customs and systems. Matrairky gender culture was formed in the Minangkabau and Kerinci communities. While patriarchal gender culture was formed in Malay society, due to the wide possibility of migrants coming to Central Sumatra, there are also Javanese and Batak ethnic groups as part of the patriarchy. So, in this research, gender culture is known when we know the culture that the child adheres to. The instrument for the career expectation variable is based on Betz's theory and how it has changed over time. This theory divides career expectation into two sub-variables: self-efficacy and OE. There are six indicators for the sub-variable "self-efficacy," and four indicators for the sub-variable "outcome expectation". This instrument was created in 3 stages, first the instrument was prepared based on Betz's theory of career expectations with two sub-varieties and ten indicators producing 38 items, then the instrument was tested for content validity by experts and also provided input regarding the content of the instrument for the development of the instrument, then the results The validity of the content was tested on a limited sample of 35 people, to see the suitability of the construct, statistical analysis was carried out using product moment with a probability value of 0.05. The results of the validity test eliminated 5 instrument items, 2 items in the SEE sub-variable and 3 items in the OE sub-variable. then reliability was carried out using Cronbach's alpha from 35 trial samples, obtaining an r value of 0.405 which was bigger than 0.339 (r table value at N = 35, sig = 5%) [8], [20]. The variables workflow can be seen at Figure 2.

In this study, the Tukey HSD one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) test is used to compare the effects of patriarchy (X1) and matriarchy (X2) on career expectation self-efficacy (Y1) and career expectation result. The information used in these analyses comes from a poll that was given to the people who took part. With the research hypothesis: i) give a quantitative description of the career expectations of students from patriarchal family cultures; ii) give a quantitative description of the career expectations of students from matriarchal family cultures; and iii) compare the career expectations of students from patriarchal and matriarchal family cultures.

Figure 2. Variable

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The study results are talked about by giving an explanation of the overall data, which comes from a summary of the data on the variables, as shown in the Table 1. This number is part of the talk of what was found. The ANOVA table presents a comparison between two sets of data: SEE and OE. In the case of SEE, we observe a highly significant difference among the groups. This is supported by a Total Sum of Squares of 2,721,652, 1 degree of freedom (DF), a mean square of 2.721, an F-statistic of 75.011, and an extremely low significance value (Sig.) of 0.000. These results indicate that the observed differences are not due to chance and hold significant statistical importance.

Similarly, for OE, the results also show a highly significant difference among the groups, with a Total Sum of Squares of 6,964,551, 1 DF, a Mean Square of 6.964, an F-statistic of 145.467, and a low significance value (Sig.) of 0.000. This confirms that the differences have high statistical significance. In summary, based on these numerical findings, it can be concluded that in this analysis, both SEE and OE exhibit significant differences among the observed groups.

Tabel 1. Result

		ANOVA				
		Sum of squares	DF	Mean square	F	Sig.
SEE	Between groups	2,721,652	1	2.721	75.011	0.000
	Within groups	3,882,311	107	36.283	-	-
	Total	6,603,963	108			
OE	Between groups	6,964,551	1	6.964	145.467	0.000
	Within groups	5,122,862	107	47.877	-	-
	Total	12,087,413	10			

3.1. Career expectations owned by women with a patriarchal culture

Figure 3, which was presented earlier, is a graphical representation of the data that differentiates the scores achieved in describing the various sorts of career expectations. The pattern demonstrates that the career kind of SEE has a comparatively high average score in comparison to the outcome expectation. There are three angles from which one might examine the differences between these two scenarios. First, the demands placed on girls in patriarchal cultures that have the function of serving the needs of the family require girls to have skills before getting responsibilities related to those skills; second, the limited political position for women in patriarchal families creates opportunities for women to try new things or hone skills; and third, education that is implemented through folklore or saga in patriarchal cultures provides teaching about heroic stories that are a model for behavior; all three of these factors contribute to the possibility for women to try new things [21]–[23]. It is possible to interpret career expectations (Y) through the lens of patriarchal family gender culture, which is dominated by self-efficacy career expectations, as stated in the earlier summary. In accordance with indicators related to self-efficacy career expectations, the three perspectives presented above are as: i) determining career choices; ii) overcoming skill barriers with practice; iii) developing skills on professionalism; iv) determining achievements; v) being service-oriented; and vi) being resolute in one's decision [6], [24].

3.2. Career expectations held by women with a matriarchal culture

In the preceding figure, referred to as Figure 4, a graph depicts a comparison of the scores obtained when characterizing the various categories of professional aspirations in matriarchal families. The graph

depicts, on average, the dominance of the various types of career outcome expectations held by individuals. This distinction is investigated from four distinct angles. The demands placed on women in matriarchal cultures to be able to manage the complex family system give women in patriarchal cultures the ability to see opportunities in every problem; second, the political position that is elevated in the family compared to men results in limitations for women in matriarchal families to develop the skills they are interested in and like; and third, education that is implemented through folklore hinders women in matriarchal cultures [25]–[28]. It is possible to see career expectations (Y) in terms of family gender culture patriarchy, which is depicted in the figure that is located above. Career outcomes expectation kinds are the ones that predominate. Indicators regarding expected career outcomes are linked to the four aforementioned perspectives. These indicators consist of: i) career adaptation or career change to attain goals; ii) skills development after obtaining responsibility; iii) recognition and appreciation; and iv) work-life balance [6], [29].

Figure 3. Conditions of career expectations on the patriarchal culture gender

Figure 4. Recapitulation of the results of data collection on the matriarchal gender culture

3.3. Comparison of women's career expectations with patriarchal and matriarchal cultures

In Table 1, the ANOVA resulted in a score that enabled a comparison of career expectations between the two cultural variants. The fact that there is a substantial difference indicates that the 109 respondents come from families with gender-specific cultures that have varying expectations for a person's career path. The appropriateness of the concept of professional education in a patriarchal family with career SEE, as well as the concept of matriarchal culture with career outcome expectations, and how these two concepts compare and contrast. Examining the characteristics of culture that are believed to be transmitted from one generation to the next may provide insight into this phenomenon. Depending on the context, this ethical aspect of culture can be attributed to patriarchal or matriarchal societies. The 109 subjects consisted of Malay communities from Jambi and Riau, known for their patriarchal culture, and Minang tribes from West Sumatra and Kerinci. In this context, "cultural aspects" refers to items such as proverbs, folklore, and saga, all of which serve an educational function and are therefore viewed favorably within the dominant cultural system. Folklore is straightforward to dissect when viewed in the context of the prevalent patriarchal culture around the globe. In Norse mythology, for instance, the god of thunder is named Thor, and he must be able to control his abilities and use them for the benefit of humanity before his father, the king of the gods Odin, can bestow upon him the crown Mjolnir as a throne and sign of his success as a god. Alternatively, there is the well-known Japanese folktale about Momotaro, who is the only person who can save his community and defeat the titans by being kind to others. In Malay culture, there is a story about a man named Hang Tuah who must oppose his brother, who has become a tyrannical ruler after leaving the kingdom, or there is a proverb that states "*raja alim mesti disembah, raja zalim mesti disanggah*" (a just king must be worshiped, while an unjust king must be refuted)." Both of these are present within the culture [30]–[34].

Matriarchal cultures have their own unique traits that are reflected in their folklore. For example, in Greek mythology there is a tribe known as Amazonia that is led by women. What makes this tribe so powerful is that it cannot be conquered by any other tribe, not even the gods. This is due to the resourcefulness of the leaders of the Amazonian tribes in changing their military tactics to that of their adversary. In addition to that, there is a folktale that comes from the region of Khasi, which is located between India and Nepal, and it tells the story of a character named Ka Nongthaw who was loved by a young man named U Suidnoh. However, their love was thwarted because of the social status of Ka Nongthaw, who was a nobleman, while U Suidnoh was just an ordinary guy. The most well-known narrative in Minangkabau culture is called "Malin Kundang," and it tells the tale of a youngster who disobeys his biological mother because he has already achieved success and is affluent, whilst his biological mother is still impoverished and appears to be getting older [32], [33], [35]–[37]. The characteristics of popular folklore can be differentiated

based on the numerous cultural contexts in which they exist. In cultures with patriarchal structures, traits such as heroism, the achievement of integrity, professional skills, and the capacity to conquer things deemed their responsibility are emphasized. The characteristics of a matriarchal society, on the other hand, place a greater emphasis on emotions, such as joy, sorrow, and challenges, and demonstrate the significance of creativity and strategy in finding solutions to problems. These two distinguishing characteristics are related to the various professional goals associated with the gender culture to which they belong.

4. CONCLUSION

There is a correlation between the types of job expectations young women have and their indecisiveness or inability to solidify their career choices. A patriarchal gender culture will foster career expectations that are confident in their abilities in relation to the work that they are engaged in, whereas a matriarchal gender culture will foster career expectations that are adaptable to any job. Individuals' career expectations are influenced by their familial and cultural learning experiences, such as folklore, saga, and proverbs.

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